

Exploring Traditional Knowledge : Bridging Past and Future

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Traditional knowledge systems / Bharatiya Knowledge Systems are dynamic as new knowledge is continuously added, adapted and altered. The systems innovate from within and internalize use and adapt external knowledge to suit local situations and thereby ensure communities' resilience to change.

Synergy between Man and Environment results into the sound Ecosystem. The Indian/Bharatiya knowledge systems have been practiced by centuries and thus are time tested and proven. Traditional and continuously developed Knowledge refers to that knowledge, where skills and practices retained by the local people. Because of fast and hasty Industrialization and modernization traditional knowledge systems are on the verge of erosion today. Visualization of the development plans should be carried out taking into consideration the science and knowledge ingrained in the culture and traditions. Conservation and Management of natural resources should reflect the local and indigenous thoughts and practices. Utilization and Regeneration concepts for biodiversity and agro ecosystem should be well defined in the progress plan. The importance of natural resources in the inclusive and holistic development, traditional knowledge systems and their vital role for conserving the natural resources, the wealth of nation should be recognized in time. We observed the important role of IKS/BKS in different segments of human life that includes intercropping techniques, pest control, crop diversity, and seed varieties in agriculture; plant varieties, and fish breeding techniques in biology; traditional medicine in human healthcare; soil conservation, irrigation, and water conservation in natural resource management; and oral traditions and local languages in education. The realization of IK's contribution to these sectors has led to an increasing interest in it by academicians, and policymakers alike. We pointed out that the challenges of sustainability in the twenty-first century across the world has created a shift in attitude towards recognizing Bharatiya knowledge and correspond it to other forms of knowledge. The serious damages to environment has made it essential to understand and incorporate IKS/BKS into the global body of knowledge for the benefit of all human kind. The significance of IKS/BKS in sustainable

development is perceived by the policy makers across the world.

Key needs neglected in the numerous initiatives underway that require further urgent attention include: Host regional meetings on for traditional knowledge. Actions are needed to:

- Host regional meetings on elder generations and youths for proper documentation of traditional knowledge: action is needed to identify and design modalities that develop capacity of future leaders in advocacy, skill building and knowledge sharing.

- Convene an expert group meeting on traditional knowledge: generation, transmission and protection to network the body of successful global experience and address emerging issues.

- Develop guidelines, tools and training courses on the use of digital technology and Traditional knowledge and its continuous development.

- Conduct research on traditional knowledge areas and their impact on protecting, transmitting and generating traditional knowledge.

- Study on innovative methodologies for revitalizing native languages among youth.